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Glossary

AC	Alternating current
AF	Antenna factor
EMI	Electromagnetic Interference
HC	Helmholtz Coils
HF	High frequency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
RF	Radio Frequency
SLA	Small Loop Antenna
TEM	Transversal Electromagnetic (e.g., wave)
VNA	Vector Network Analyser

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Summary

The research presented in this report includes the design, fabrication and characterisation of the Helmholtz coils setup up to 10 MHz using various methods. For this purpose, a single-turn shielded small loop antenna and commercial magnetic field probes are used and the results are compared. In addition, to use loop antennas as a calibration transfer standard, the magnetic antenna factors obtained by different calibration methods of loop antennas are compared by including the uncertainty budget of each method. As a result of the evaluation, the magnetic antenna factors obtained by the impedance method of small loop antennas were used to calibrate the magnetic field strength indicated in Helmholtz coils.

1. INTRODUCTION

This document describes investigations regarding the evaluation of an improved calibration method for the extension of the existing magnetic field calibration capability in Helmholtz coils from 3 MHz to 10 MHz or higher frequencies.

In the scope of the project, Helmholtz coils were designed and fabricated. The fabricated Helmholtz coils were characterised with respect to field generation, time stability and uniformity of the field, current measurement and coil geometry parameters. All the research was considered to increase the maximum achievable frequency range of the Helmholtz coils. As a result, a calibration method was determined and agreed the by the participant institutes. This report includes an Improved calibration method for the extension of the existing magnetic field calibration capability in Helmholtz coils from 3 MHz to 10 MHz.

The standard IEEE 1309 defines calibration methods of the magnetic field probes which include evaluating the Helmholtz coils calibration setup. Generally, Helmholtz coils use frequencies up to hundreds of kHz. Construction of the Helmholtz coils suitable for higher frequencies needs a special design and careful optimization. Fabricating Helmholtz coils suitable for MHz frequencies brings some issues such as the shielding effect of the cables, cable loss, parasitic effects causing loading material, limited cable length, and appropriate transfer standard. Traditionally, the establishment of the magnetic field strength traceability for Helmholtz coils calibration is based on current measurement as a calculable method. The accuracy of the magnetic field generated in the pair of Helmholtz coils is primarily affected by the accuracy with which they are constructed, the dimensions and the accuracy with which the current driving them is measured. Also, parameters such as material dielectric constant, coil geometry and cable diameters play critical roles in the fabrication of the Helmholtz coils.

This report provides fabrication methods and characterization techniques of the Helmholtz coils in the frequency range of 3 MHz to 10 MHz and research outputs of the extension of the Helmholtz coil calibration frequency range above 10 MHz.

The report content flow is as follows:

Chapter 2 discusses the design and fabrication of the Helmholtz coils and the results of their characterization. In Chapter 3, various loop antenna calibrations are included to determine the most suitable method for calibrating Helmholtz coils. Calibration of the fabricated Helmholtz coils is performed according to the determined calibration method. In Chapter 4, the calibration of a magnetic field probe is carried out by two different methods: the Helmholtz coil and the TEM cell method, respectively. In Chapter 5, a discussion on the measured results and methods is given together with the future research outlook.

2. DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF THE HELMHOLTZ COILS

The size of the coils and the required field strength have a significant impact on ensuring both the maximum calibration frequency and the minimum environmental conditions. Coil geometry is also important to ensure the field uniformity for a field probe/sensor calibration. Therefore, the number of windings is an important parameter to produce magnetic fields at the desired level. However, it is more difficult to work in the high-frequency region in a multi-turn coil. Therefore, building Helmholtz coils that can operate at high frequencies without compromising field level may not be a cost-effective goal. The Helmholtz coils designed in this project have a single winding and a diameter of 30 cm. The coils are made of a 5 mm diameter wire.

The designed Helmholtz coils were characterized using the following parameters:

- Coil geometry
- Uniformity
- Power stability
- Current measurement

2.1 Characterization Measurements

2.1.1 Coil Geometry

The manufactured Helmholtz coil dimensions in the scope of the project are given in Table 1. Upper frequencies are limited as a major parameter by the cable length and wire diameter of the Helmholtz coils [1]. The material used in coil winding may create parasitic effects. At MHz frequencies, the cables used for serial connection of coils begin to radiate and create a secondary magnetic field due to the electric field based on Maxwell equations. For this reason, it is important to shield, ground and separate the cables from each other.

Table 1. Helmholtz coils dimensions

Parameter	Value
r	15.25 cm
a	7.5 cm
Wire diameter	5 mm
N	1

r : is the radius of the coils

a : is the half of the distance between coils and $a=r/2$

N : is the number of turns

Helmholtz coils were characterized by a VNA. The measurement setup photo is shown in Fig. 1. Some of the measured results are given in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Fig. 1 Characterization measurements of the manufactured Helmholtz coils.

Fig. 2 Helmholtz coils theta measurement results.

Fig. 3 S₁₁ (input reflection coefficient) measurements VNA display of the Helmholtz coils.

According to impedance measurement results we propose the usage of the Helmholtz coils in the frequency range 3 MHz to 10 MHz. The impedance characteristic of the Helmholtz coils is flat above 14 MHz due to parasitic circuit elements and imperfections errors.

2.1.2 Uniformity of the Helmholtz coils

For the Helmholtz coils [3], two equal coils carrying equal current are used one on each side of the experimental area, separated by a distance R , which is also the radius of each coil. If the experimental area is centred at $x = 0$, then the x coordinates of both coils are at $x_{1,2} = \pm(R/2)$. This arrangement minimizes the non-uniformity of the magnetic field at the centre of the coils [2]. Uniform field area measurements of the manufactured Helmholtz coils were performed using a TUBITAK UME made small loop antenna (SLA) used for magnetic field measurements, for which its reference magnetic field was calculated based on antenna factors of the small loop antenna. The orientation of the Helmholtz coils during the measurement and the range of measurement points is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Uniformity measurement setup (not shown x-axis)

The Helmholtz coils magnetic field uniformity measurements were performed using a calibrated small loop antenna at the AC magnetic field. The uniformity measurements were performed at two axes of the Helmholtz coils. Uniformity measurements were performed at the midpoint of the Helmholtz coils. The value of the magnetic field indicated along the y-axis and x-axis at the centre of the coils is 0.47 A/m, while the calculated field uses nominal current and coil dimensions separately. The small loop antenna was positioned on the slider to move it linearly only along the relevant axis, and measurements were carried out in a total of 28 points along the y-axis and 18 points for the x-axis. In order not to be affected by the earth's magnetic field during the measurements, the measurements were performed at the AC frequencies. The resolution of the small loop antenna is dependent on the EMI receiver. The small loop antenna has a circular geometry and its diameter is 5 cm and returns magnetic field Peak+ values on the EMI receiver. The magnetic field strength values measured along the y-axis were normalized and are given in Fig. 5. The magnetic field strength values measured along the x-axis were normalized and are given in Fig. 6. The main measurement uncertainty contributions are the Helmholtz coils dimensions, signal stability, axial symmetry of the measurement axis, alignment and the measurement repeatability. The schematic of the measurement setup is given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5 Measured uniformity of the magnetic field strength results for a 30 cm Helmholtz coils along the y-axis. Measurements were performed with a small loop antenna at a theoretical current 0.099 A through the coils.

Fig. 6 Measured uniformity of the magnetic field strength results for a 30 cm Helmholtz coil along the x-axis. Measurements were performed with a small loop antenna at a theoretical current 0.099 A through the coils.

a)

b)

Fig. 7 Photos from the uniformity field measurement setup, (a) along y-axis measurement and (b) along x-axis measurement

2.1.3 Time Stability

Time stability measurements were performed at 10 MHz frequency and 0.47 A/m magnetic field strength value at the uniformity measurement setup via a small loop antenna. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 8. The current measurement was performed using a harmonic signal and 50 Ω load on the used oscilloscope.

Fig. 8 Time stability measurement results of the Helmholtz coils calibration setup.

2.1.4 Magnetic Field Generation

The magnetic field strength value of Helmholtz coils consisting of two identical coils can be calculated by using the equation below

$$H_x = \frac{NIr^2}{(r^2+a^2)^{3/2}}, \quad (1)$$

where

N : is the number of turns

r : is the radius of each coil (m)

x : is the axial position of the magnetic field (m) from the centre of the coil set

I : is the coil current in the coils (A)

2.1.5 Current Measurement

To produce magnetic field strength apply a signal from the signal generator to the RF amplifier and connect the output of the RF amplifier to the Helmholtz coil with at least 6 dB/250 W attenuator (not shown in Fig. 9) to prevent the amplifier from reflections due to impedance mismatch. The magnetic field strength can be calculated by getting the measured current values from the voltage on the 50 Ω load using an oscilloscope. To be sure the signal profile is exact, display the sinus signal on the oscilloscope. The current value can be

calculated using exact impedance values of the 50 Ω load from the calibration certificate / datasheet for each frequency.

The measurement setup of the magnetic field strength at measurements is given in Fig. 9. The photos from the measurements are shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. The manufactured Helmholtz coils are shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 9 The measurement setup of the magnetic field strength calibration in the Helmholtz coils.

Fig. 10 Photo of the measurement setup using a small loop antenna.

Fig. 11 Measurement setup using the HF 3061 magnetic field probe.

Fig. 12 Manufactured Helmholtz coils cover a frequency range of 3 MHz to 10 MHz.

To correct the magnetic field strength value in the HF (High frequency) Helmholtz coils, a commercial magnetic field probe and loop antenna were used. The used antenna and probe information are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Information of the used magnetic field probe and loop antenna

No	Method	Manufacturer	Probe Model	Monitor Model	Frequency Range
1	Magnetic Field Probe	Narda Safety Test Solutions	HF 3061	NBM550	300 kHz-30 MHz
2	Loop antenna	Schwarzbeck	HFRA 5154	-	100 kHz-30 MHz

3. CALIBRATION METHOD

Correction of the field strength value in the Helmholtz coils proposes the loop antenna factor method. For this purpose, the loop antenna method was evaluated. Firstly, loop antenna factors were compared and three general loop antenna calibration methods were used, such as the Impedance method [3], SAE/ARP958 [4] and the three-antenna method [5], respectively.

3.1 Comparison of the Magnetic Antenna Factors using different calibration methods

To check the magnetic antenna factors obtained from the impedance measurements, different methods such as the three-antenna method and the SAE/ARP958 method were tested.

3.1.1 Impedance Method

The impedance method is a proposed magnetic antenna factor method to calibrate the Helmholtz coils at high frequencies. The impedance method makes it possible for more rigid loop antenna calibration, includes impedance correction and makes it more reliable with lower uncertainties of the Helmholtz coils calibration.

The antenna factor is defined as the ratio of an incident electric field to the corresponding output voltage across the matched load [3]. Magnetic antenna factor can be defined as follows for the loop antenna shown in Fig. 13

$$F_m(f) = \frac{H(f)}{V_o(f)}, \quad (2)$$

where H is the magnetic field strength of the electromagnetic plane-wave incident on the antenna element and V_o is the output voltage across the load.

Fig. 13 Structure of a shielded loop antenna.

The small loop antenna can be modelled as shown in Fig. 14a Fig. 14b.

Fig. 14 Equivalent circuits of a shielded loop antenna (a) Equivalent circuit of the loop antenna shown in Fig. 13 (b) Remodelled circuit of (a)

Magnetic antenna factors can be obtained by finding parameters in the equations (3) and (4)

$$Z'_R = Z_0 \frac{Z_R + Z_0 \tanh(jkL_2)}{Z_0 + Z_R \tanh(jkL_2)} \tag{3}$$

$$Z'_L = Z_0 \frac{Z_L + Z_0 \tanh(jkL_1)}{Z_0 + Z_L \tanh(jkL_1)} \tag{4}$$

Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of the transmission line (50 Ω), L_1 and L_2 are the half lengths of the loop elements, Z_R is the load impedance at one end of the compensation circuit (most of the time it is short, i.e. 0 Ω), and Z_L is the match load to the line impedance (50 Ω) and $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wavenumber and λ is the wavelength in the cable.

Open-circuit output voltage V of the loop antenna element is expressed by Faraday's law as in equation (5)

$$V = -j\omega\pi r^2 \mu_0 H, \quad (5)$$

where ω is the angular frequency, r is the radius of the loop antenna, μ_0 is the permeability of the free space, and H is the magnetic field strength of the incident plane wave.

In our case, a normalization is needed from the open circuit output voltage to our 50 Ω impedance. The simulated open circuit voltage for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 10 cm diameter antenna in the revised form is shown in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15 Obtaining the open circuit output voltage for a 50 Ω impedance loop antenna.

In this case, the revised open circuit output voltage can be defined as follows.

$$V'_{OC} = Z_{loop} \frac{V_{OC}}{Z_S + Z_{loop}}, \quad (6)$$

provided the measured impedance values of the loop antenna with the line characteristic impedance are written instead of Z_{loop} and Z_S in equation (6), respectively.

Finally, the magnetic antenna factor of this shielded loop antenna is expressed as

$$F_m(\omega) = \frac{H}{V'_L} = j \frac{Z'_R + Z_{in} + Z'_L}{\omega \mu_0 \pi r^2 Z_L} \frac{Z_L + Z_0}{Z'_L + Z_0} e^{jkL_1}, \quad (7)$$

where

$$Z_{in} = \frac{Z_0(Z''_{in} - Z'_R) + (Z''_{in} Z'_R - Z_0^2) \tanh(jkL_1)}{Z_0 - Z''_{in} \tanh(jkL_1)}, \quad (8)$$

V'_L is the voltage at terminal #1 and Z''_{in} is the input impedance at terminal #1. Calculation of the magnetic antenna factor only needs measurement of the loop antenna impedance Z''_{in} .

Magnetic antenna factor measurements are performed using equations (7) and (8) using the impedance method. The measurement results are given in Table 3. For measurements, we used the Schwarzbeck model HFRA 5154 loop antenna.

Table 3. Impedance and magnetic antenna factor of the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna

Frequency (MHz)	Impedance Real (Ω)	Impedance Imag (Ω)	Magnetic Antenna Factor (dB(S/m))	Simulated Magnetic Antenna Factor (dB(S/m))
0.1	48.59	5.59	50.06	50.27
0.2	49.09	2.80	44.07	44.22
0.3	49.13	1.88	40.55	40.70
0.4	49.14	1.43	38.06	38.20
0.5	49.15	1.17	36.12	36.26
0.6	49.16	0.99	34.53	34.68
0.7	49.17	0.87	33.20	33.34
0.8	49.19	0.78	32.04	32.18
0.9	49.20	0.71	31.02	31.16
1	49.22	0.65	30.10	30.24
2	49.37	0.33	24.10	24.21
3	49.47	0.11	20.58	20.68
4	49.51	-0.09	18.09	18.17
5	49.52	-0.26	16.15	16.23
6	49.49	-0.42	14.57	14.65
7	49.45	-0.56	13.22	13.32
8	49.39	-0.67	12.06	12.16
9	49.33	-0.77	11.03	11.14
10	49.25	-0.86	10.11	10.24
11	49.16	-0.92	9.28	9.42
12	49.07	-0.97	8.51	8.67
13	48.98	-0.99	7.81	7.98
14	48.89	-1.00	7.16	7.35
15	48.79	-0.99	6.55	6.76
16	48.70	-0.96	5.98	6.20
17	48.61	-0.91	5.45	5.68
18	48.53	-0.84	4.95	5.20
19	48.46	-0.76	4.47	4.73
20	48.40	-0.66	4.02	4.29
21	48.34	-0.55	3.59	3.87
22	48.31	-0.42	3.18	3.47
23	48.28	-0.29	2.79	3.09
24	48.27	-0.14	2.42	2.72
25	48.28	0.01	2.06	2.37
26	48.30	0.17	1.72	2.02
27	48.35	0.33	1.40	1.69
28	48.41	0.50	1.08	1.37

29	48.50	0.66	0.78	1.06
30	48.60	0.82	0.50	0.75

3.1.1.1 Measurement Uncertainty for Impedance Method

The uncertainty budget for the antenna factors of the loop antenna obtained by the impedance method is given in Table 4.

Table 4. Uncertainty budget for impedance method

Source of uncertainty	Definition	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
U_{VNA}	S parameter	B	0.020	Normal	2	1	0.001
δ_R	Reflections	B	0.058	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.033
U_{r1}	Diameter error for antenna	B	0.070	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.040
δ_M	Mismatch	B	0.170	U-type	1.414	1	0.120
Total Standard Uncertainty (k=2)							0.260

3.1.2 SAEARP958 Method

Loop antenna calibration was carried out by the SAEARP958 standard [4]. The definition of the loop antenna calibration is given in Section 6 of the standard. A schematic of a single-turn loop antenna as a calculable standard is shown in Fig 16.

Fig. 16 Single-turn loop antenna as a calculable standard

The open circuit voltage of the single-turn loop antenna is given in equations (9) to (11). Finally, the magnetic antenna factor of the single-turn loop antenna is given in equation (12).

$$V_0 = NBA\omega \quad (9)$$

$$V_0 = \mu_0 H \pi r_1^2 2\pi f \quad (10)$$

$$V_L = V_0 \frac{R_L}{R_L + R_C + jX_C} \quad (11)$$

$$AF = \frac{H}{V_L} = \frac{\sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{R_C}{R_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2\pi f L}{R_L}\right)^2}}{\mu_0 \pi r_1^2 2\pi f} \quad (12)$$

3.1.3 Measurement Uncertainty for SAEARP958 Method

The impedance method uncertainty budget is given in Table 4 and can be used for calibrations performed according to the SAEARP 958 method.

3.1.4 Three Antenna Method

The magnetic antenna factor of a loop antenna is defined as the ratio of the incident plane magnetic field strength to the output voltage of the matched load. However, it is difficult to apply the actual plane wave to a loop antenna or obtain even a quasi-far-field condition at the low frequency (in the frequency range below 30 MHz). This method requires three loop antennas taken in pairs and yields the factors of each loop antenna separately as seen in Fig. 17 [4], [5].

Fig. 17 Three antenna loop calibration method

$$AF_{mi}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{-A_{jk}\alpha_{ij}\alpha_{ik}}{A_{ij}A_{ik}\alpha_{jk}}} \quad (13)$$

$$(i, j, k) = (1,2,3)(2,1,3)(3,1,2) \quad (14)$$

Where

$$\alpha_{lm} = \frac{\sqrt{1 + R_{lm}^2 k^2}}{j\omega\mu_0\pi Z_L R_{lm}^3} \left\{ 1 + \frac{15(r_l r_m)^2}{8R_{lm}^4} + \frac{315(r_l r_m)^4}{64 R_{lm}^8} \right\} \quad (15)$$

$$R_{lm} = \sqrt{d_{lm}^2 + r_l^2 + r_m^2} \quad (16)$$

$$(l, m) = (1,2), (1,3), (2,3) \quad (17)$$

AF_{mi} is the i -th loop antenna's magnetic antenna factor,

k is the wave number ($=2\pi/\lambda$), λ is the free-space wavelength,

A_{12} , A_{13} , A_{23} are the transmission S-parameters between the antennas,

ω is the angular frequency,

μ_0 is the permeability of free space,

Z_L is the load impedance matched to the transmission line,

r_1 , r_2 , r_3 are the radii of the loop antennas,

d_{12} , d_{13} , d_{23} are the distances between the two loop antennas.

3.1.4.1 Measurement Uncertainty for 3-Antenna Calibration Method

The model function and uncertainty budget of the antenna factors of the loop antenna obtained with the 3-antenna method are given in Tables 5 to 7. The total measurement uncertainty is given in Table 7 using the partial uncertainty values obtained from Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. Partial uncertainty budget of S-parameter and environmental errors

Source of uncertainty	Definition	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
U_{NA-A23}	V_{S21} Linearity	B	0.230	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.133
δ_{R-A23}	Reflections	B	0.058	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.033
δ_{Ax-A23}	Alignment error centre of the loop antennas	B	0.008	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.005
δ_{Ar-A23}	Angle error between loop antennas	B	0.010	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.006
δ_{M-A23}	Mismatch between antennas	B	0.170	U-type	1.414	1	0.120
Total Standard Uncertainty ($k=1$)							0.180

Table 6. Partial uncertainty budget of mechanical faults

Source of uncertainty	Definition	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
U_{d12}	Measurement Distance (Antenna1-2)	B	0.172	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.099
U_{d13}	Measurement Distance (Antenna1-3)	B	0.172	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.099
U_{d23}	Measurement Distance (Antenna2-3)	B	0.172	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.099
U_{r1}	Diameter error for Antenna 1	B	0.341	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.197
U_{r2}	Diameter error for Antenna 2	B	0.341	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.197
U_{r3}	Diameter error for Antenna 3	B	0.341	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.197
δ_D	Distribution error of the magnetic field	B	0.108	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.062
Total Standard Uncertainty ($k=1$)							0.390

Table 7. Total measurement uncertainty budget for the 3-antenna method

Source of uncertainty	Definition	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
U_{Aij}	$A_{i,j}$	-	0.180	-	-	0.866	0.156
U_{Aik}	$A_{i,k}$	-	0.180	-	-	0.866	0.156
U_{Ajk}	$A_{j,k}$	-	0.180	-	-	0.866	0.156
U_{alm}	α_{lm}	-	0.390	-	-	0.866	0.338
δ_{Rep}	Repeatability	-	0.000	-	-	1.000	0.000
Total Standard Uncertainty ($k=1$)							0.430
Total Measurement Uncertainty ($k=2$)							0.860

3.1.5 Comparison of the magnetic antenna factors using different calibration methods

Loop antenna calibrations needed for more reliable determination of magnetic antenna factors were carried out using different calibration methods. All the results were compared and the summary is given in Table 8 for the hand-made small loop antenna and in Table 9 for the Schwarzbeck HFRA5154 loop antenna. The results are shown in Fig. 18 for the handmade small loop antenna and in Fig. 19 for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna. The Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna was used as a transfer standard to perform the calibration of the Helmholtz coils.

Table 8. Comparison of the magnetic antenna factors using different calibration methods for TUBITAK UME made 5 cm diameter small loop antenna

Frequency (MHz)	Three antenna method AF (dB(S/m))	Impedance method (dB(S/m))	SAEARP958 Method (dB(S/m))	Simulation results (dB(S/m))
0.1	55.43	55.51	55.51	56.19
0.2	49.39	49.49	49.49	50.17
0.3	45.89	45.97	45.97	46.65
0.4	43.40	43.47	43.47	44.15
0.5	41.45	41.54	41.54	42.21
0.6	39.87	39.95	39.95	40.63
0.7	38.53	38.61	38.61	39.29
0.8	37.37	37.45	37.45	38.13
0.9	36.36	36.43	36.43	37.11
1	35.44	35.52	35.52	36.19
2	29.42	29.50	29.51	30.17
3	25.91	25.99	25.99	26.65
4	23.41	23.50	23.51	24.15
5	21.48	21.58	21.59	22.21
6	19.90	20.01	20.02	20.63
7	18.58	18.69	18.71	19.29
8	17.44	17.56	17.57	18.13
9	16.44	16.56	16.58	17.11

Frequency (MHz)	Three antenna method AF (dB(S/m))	Impedance method (dB(S/m))	SAEARP958 Method (dB(S/m))	Simulation results (dB(S/m))
10	15.56	15.67	15.70	16.19
11	14.75	14.87	14.90	15.36
12	14.02	14.15	14.19	14.61
13	13.36	13.48	13.53	13.91
14	12.74	12.88	12.93	13.27
15	12.17	12.32	12.38	12.67
16	11.64	11.80	11.87	12.11
17	11.15	11.32	11.40	11.58
18	10.68	10.86	10.96	11.09
19	10.25	10.44	10.54	10.62
20	9.84	10.05	10.16	10.17
21	9.45	9.68	9.80	9.75
22	9.09	9.33	9.46	9.34
23	8.74	9.00	9.15	8.96
24	8.41	8.69	8.85	8.59
25	8.10	8.40	8.57	8.23
26	7.80	8.12	8.31	7.89
27	7.52	7.86	8.06	7.56
28	7.25	7.61	7.83	7.25
29	6.99	7.37	7.61	6.94
30	6.73	7.15	7.41	6.65

Fig. 18 Comparison results of the magnetic antenna factors for TUBITAK UME made small loop antenna.

In Fig. 18, the maximum difference between the simulation and the experiment is approx. ± 0.3 dB for the 10 cm diameter Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna.

Table 9. Comparison of the magnetic antenna factors using different calibration method Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154

Frequency (MHz)	Three antenna method AF (dB(S/m))	Impedance method (dB(S/m))	SAEARP958 Method (dB(S/m))	Simulation results dB(S/m)
0.1	49.99	50.06	50.06	50.27
0.2	43.98	44.07	44.07	44.22
0.3	40.47	40.55	40.55	40.70
0.4	37.96	38.06	38.06	38.20
0.5	36.03	36.12	36.12	36.26
0.6	34.44	34.53	34.54	34.68
0.7	33.11	33.20	33.20	33.34
0.8	31.94	32.04	32.04	32.18
0.9	30.92	31.02	31.02	31.16
1	30.00	30.10	30.10	30.24
2	23.97	24.10	24.10	24.21
3	20.44	20.58	20.58	20.68
4	17.93	18.09	18.09	18.17
5	15.99	16.15	16.15	16.23
6	14.40	14.57	14.56	14.65
7	13.07	13.22	13.22	13.32
8	11.92	12.06	12.06	12.16
9	10.90	11.03	11.03	11.14
10	9.99	10.11	10.11	10.24
11	9.16	9.28	9.27	9.42
12	8.41	8.51	8.51	8.67
13	7.71	7.81	7.80	7.98
14	7.07	7.16	7.15	7.35
15	6.46	6.55	6.54	6.76
16	5.90	5.98	5.98	6.20
17	5.37	5.45	5.44	5.68
18	4.87	4.95	4.94	5.20
19	4.39	4.47	4.46	4.73
20	3.94	4.02	4.01	4.29
21	3.51	3.59	3.58	3.87
22	3.09	3.18	3.17	3.47
23	2.70	2.79	2.79	3.09
24	2.32	2.42	2.42	2.72
25	1.96	2.06	2.06	2.37
26	1.61	1.72	1.72	2.02
27	1.27	1.40	1.40	1.69
28	0.94	1.08	1.09	1.37
29	0.63	0.78	0.79	1.06
30	0.32	0.50	0.51	0.75

Fig. 19 Comparison results of the magnetic antenna factors for Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154.

For a detailed evaluation, the differences for the Schwarzbeck HFRA5154 antenna can be seen in Fig. 20.

Fig. 20 Differences between the three methods for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 antenna

The presented magnetic antenna factors can be used as a reference to perform the calibration of the Helmholtz coils up to 10 MHz. Since the antenna factors obtained in the measurements made by all three methods are very close to each other, the antenna factors can also be used to verify/calibrate Helmholtz coils. The methods only differ in the achieved measurement uncertainty. Antenna factors with lower uncertainty should be preferred for calibrating Helmholtz coils.

4. VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

Magnetic antenna factors were adapted to the calibration of the Helmholtz coils. To validate this method, a comparison with other experimental methods was performed. This kind of validation also presents a proposed evaluation of the end-user antenna calibration.

4.1 Helmholtz coil measurements

Firstly, a small loop antenna was inserted in the centre of the Helmholtz coils in the sensing axis of the indicated magnetic field strength. To get the AC voltage values from the loop antenna, the Rohde&Schwarz ESIB40 EMI receiver was used. Measurements were performed with 0.2 A/m magnetic field strength for the whole frequency range. The EMI receiver was set to peak+ detector for Input 2. The measurements were performed for both the TUBITAK UME-made small loop antenna with a diameter of 5 cm and the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 model loop antenna, respectively. The magnetic loop antenna factors were obtained by dividing the magnetic field strength H value (A/m) by the voltage output value indicated at the small loop antenna output by using the EMI receiver. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 21 and the photos from the measurements are shown in Fig. 22 and Fig. 23.

Fig. 21 The schematic diagram of the Helmholtz coils measurement setup.

Fig. 22 Photo of the measurement setup with the small loop antenna in Helmholtz coils.

Fig. 23 Photo of the measurement setup with the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna in Helmholtz coils.

The measurement results of the TUBITAK UME-made small loop antenna and Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 model loop antenna in the Helmholtz coils are given in Table 10.

Table 10. The magnetic antenna factors for TUBITAK UME made small loop antenna and Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 model loop antenna in the newly manufactured Helmholtz coil calibration setup

Frequency (MHz)	AF of the TUBITAK UME small loop antenna (dB(S/m))	AF of the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna (dB(S/m))
3	25.321	21.221
4	22.821	18.621
5	20.921	16.821
6	19.321	15.121
7	18.021	13.821
8	17.021	12.821
9	16.021	11.721
10	15.221	10.821

4.1.1 Measurement Uncertainty for Helmholtz Coil Measurements

The components of the calibration uncertainty budget and the total calibration uncertainty are given in Table 11 below.

Table 11. Uncertainty budgets and the total calibration uncertainty for HC coil calibrations

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Calibration of Helmholtz coil	B	0.260	Normal	2	1	0.130
Reflections from the HC windings	B	0.200	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.115
Calibration of oscilloscope	B	0.150	Normal	2	1	0.075
Calibration of 50 Ohm termination	B	0.027	Normal	2	1	0.014
Non uniformity of field @x-axis	B	0.070	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.040
Non uniformity of field @y-axis	B	0.026	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.015
Time Stability	B	0.050	Normal	1	1	0.050
Misalignment	B	0.100	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.058
Repeatability	A	0.050	Normal	1	1	0.050
Total Measurement Uncertainty (k=2)						0.430

4.2 TEM cell measurements

The measurements of the small antenna factors also were performed in TEM cells. The TEM cell used was the IFI CC-102S model with the septum height of 45 cm. The TEM cell measurements were carried out at 0.1 A/m field strength. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 24. The TEM cell measurement results are given Table 12.

Fig. 24 Measurement setup in TEM cell

Table 12. Magnetic antenna factors obtained in TEM cells

Frequency (MHz)	AF of the TUBITAK UME small loop antenna (dB(S/m))	AF of the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna (dB(S/m))
3	24.279	20.199
4	21.729	17.729
5	19.919	15.789
6	18.409	14.199
7	16.999	12.809
8	16.089	11.869
9	14.909	10.609
10	13.999	9.809

The correction factors used for the Helmholtz coils are the magnetic antenna factors of the loop antenna obtained by the Impedance method. First, a calibration was performed using the HF3061 probe to observe the difference between the TEM cell and the Helmholtz coils without assigning a correction factor to the Helmholtz coils. Afterwards, with the help of loop antenna factors, the correction factors obtained for the theoretical field levels of the Helmholtz coil were used and the differences were calculated again. It can be seen that the results are much more consistent.

A comparison of all the magnetic antenna factors for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 using different calibration methods is shown in Fig. 25.

Fig. 25 All the magnetic antenna factors comparison of the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna.

The differences among all five methods are more clearly shown in Fig. 26.

Fig. 26 The differences among the 5 methods for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna (the Impedance method as a reference).

To see the effect of different calibration setups on the determination of the HF 3061 magnetic field probe factors, measurements in Helmholtz coils and TEM cells were carried out. A comparison of the correction factors for the HF 3061 magnetic field probe is shown in Fig. 27.

Fig. 27 Correction factor comparison results for the HF 3061 magnetic field probe using the TEM cell and Helmholtz coils method, respectively, before the Helmholtz coils correction.

When choosing the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 model loop antenna as a reference standard for the magnetic field strength, the coil constants and comparison results are shown in Fig. 28.

Fig. 28 Revised Helmholtz coils and TEM cell field constants correction factor comparison results for the HF 3061 magnetic field probe and differences between the two methods.

The TEM cell method is more appropriate for the HF 3061 magnetic field probe, whereas the Helmholtz coils method is more appropriate for the Schwarzbeck HFRA 5154 loop antenna.

4.2.1 TEM cell Measurement Uncertainty

Uncertainty calculations of the magnetic field strength values determined using the TEM cell constant obtained with the help of the loop antenna factor and the components of the uncertainty budget are explained in Table 13.

Table 13. Components of the uncertainty budgets of the calibration and the total calibration uncertainty

Source of uncertainty	Type	Value (dB)	Probability distribution	k-factor	Sensitivity coefficient	Standard Uncertainty (dB)
Calibration of power meter with sensor	B	0.100	Normal	2	0.500	0.025
Calibration of attenuator	B	0.300	Normal	2	0.500	0.075
TEM cell septum distance	B	0.080	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.046
Field homogeneity	B	0.320	Rectangular	1.732	1	0.185
TEM cell impedance	B	0.287	Rectangular	1.732	0.500	0.083
TEM cell output mismatch	B	0.081	U-shape	1.414	0.500	0.029
Repeatability	A	0.062	Normal	1	1	0.062
Total Uncertainty (k=2)						0.470

5. CONCLUSION

In magnetic field probe calibrations, the magnetic field intensity value is usually determined by measuring the current at low frequencies or calculating using the coil constant. However, as we move to higher frequencies, each circuit element used begins to behave like an antenna element because Ampere's law states that an alternating magnetic field induces an electric field. In this case, many parameters such as shielding at high frequencies, grounding, and parasitic effects caused by the material of the coil pulley, cable diameters, distances between cable connections, positions of the feed point, etc. exist as issues that need to be evaluated one by one. Whether each development makes a positive or negative contribution depends on the frequency. Loop antennas, whose magnetic antenna factors are usually calibrated with low uncertainties, improve the reliability of the calibration at this stage. Repeatability is the most frequently encountered uncertainty issue in antenna calibration methods, such as the 3-antenna method, which is mostly dependent on mechanical errors, operator dependence, far-field conditions and similarities of the antennas. However, in a loop antenna calibration method such as the one proposed in this report, where the antenna factors are based entirely on impedance measurement, the repeatability is very high and operator dependency is minimal.

In this study, it has been shown that it is possible to calibrate Helmholtz coils and even TEM cells at high frequencies with the factors obtained from this method. It was also observed how the Helmholtz coils and the TEM cell calibration constants obtained by this method affect the calibration of a commercial magnetic field

probe. From the results of the research, it is confirmed that the calibration of high frequency Helmholtz coils can be realised with the method proposed in this study.

In the future, in addition to these calibration methods, project proposals are planned for the implementation and standardisation of quantum detection and calculation methods at the primary level, where magnetic field strength traceability is based on universal constants such as the gyromagnetic ratio (see, e.g., [7]).

Consequently, the magnetic antenna factors obtained from the impedance method using the S_{11} values of small loop antennas were obtained. Using the obtained magnetic antenna factors, the frequency-dependent Helmholtz coils constant values were obtained in the magnetic field traceability chain.

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